

DETERMINATION OF THE SPACE GROUP OF THE CRYSTALS OF *O*-, *M*- AND *P*- NITROBENZOIC ACIDS.

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Crystallographic measurements of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids have been made and their space groups affixed

In the study of these crystals K_{α} radiations from a copper anti-cathode were used. The rotation photographs and oscillation photographs at an interval of 15° or 10° about the principal axes of the crystals, were taken by means of Bernal's photogoniometer and the latter were interpreted by means of Bernal's chart.

o-Nitrobenzoic Acid.

The crystals of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid are found to develop the following faces :

$$a(100), b'(0\bar{1}0), m(110) \text{ and } c(001).$$

They belong to the triclinic pinacoidal class and the values of α , β and γ and the axial ratio, calculated by Steinmetz from the crystallographic measurements in two different ways are :

$$\text{I.} \quad \alpha = 131^{\circ} \cdot 11\frac{1}{2}', \quad \beta = 109^{\circ} \cdot 37', \quad \gamma = 61^{\circ} \cdot 54\frac{1}{2}';$$
$$a : b : c = 0 \cdot 5364 : 1 : 0 \cdot 3576.$$

$$\text{II.} \quad \alpha = 48^{\circ} \cdot 48\frac{1}{2}', \quad \beta = 61^{\circ} \cdot 54\frac{1}{2}', \quad \gamma = 109^{\circ} \cdot 37';$$
$$a : b : c = 1 \cdot 5098 : 1 : 2 \cdot 7963.$$

(*cf.* Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie", Vol. IV, p. 472).

Crystals of the substance were obtained from dilute alcohol but it was found that the same type of crystals can be obtained from a solution of the substance in distilled water.

The lengths of the axes determined from the rotation photographs (Plate I, FIG. 1—3) about a , b and c axes are: $a = 7 \cdot 58 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 14 \cdot 01 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5 \cdot 05 \text{ \AA}$.

These rotation photographs were obtained when the setting of the crystal was done with values of α , β and γ , given in the first data. These lengths give an axial ratio $a : b : c = 0 \cdot 541 : 1 : 0 \cdot 361$, which is in good agreement with the first data of Steinmetz.

The list of reflecting planes in the crystal along with their approximate relative intensities is given in Tables I and II.

It appears from these data that there are no abnormal halvings. The crystals, therefore, belong to the space group C_1^1 which requires two asymmetric molecules for the unit cell. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the density of the crystals which was found to be 1.559 is also 2. This shows that one chemical molecule of the substance represents the asymmetric unit of the unit cell.

The ratio of the axes given in the second data of Steinmetz can be obtained from the lengths of the axes obtained above if the b and c axes are interchanged. This interchange was done by Steinmetz with a view to obtain a high value for the parameter ω because the corresponding value for the crystal of benzoic acid is also high. But the value of α in the second data is the supplement of the value of α in the first data and consequently the number of molecules in the unit cell calculated from the second data comes out to be 0.46 which is absurd. Also it has been found impossible to interpret the oscillation photographs with the values of α , β and γ given in the second data. These observations, therefore, establish that the first crystallographic data is the correct one.

m-Nitrobenzoic Acid (stable modification).

Crystals of the substance obtained from alcohol or water are found to develop the $c(001)$ and $q(011)$ faces. They belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and the axial ratio obtained from the crystallographic measurements is $a : b : c = 0.9656 : 1 : 1.2326$ and $\beta = 91^\circ.11\frac{1}{2}'$ (cf. Groth, *ibid*, p. 475).

The lengths of the axes calculated from the rotation photographs (Plate II, FIG. 1—3) about the principal axes are

$$a = 10.41 \text{ \AA}, b = 10.69 \text{ \AA}, c = 13.22 \text{ \AA}.$$

These give the axial ratio $a : b : c = 0.973 : 1 : 1.236$ which is in good agreement with that given above.

The list of reflecting planes in the crystal with their approximate relative intensities is given in Tables III and IV which show that the planes (hol) are halved when h is odd and (010) is also halved. The crystal, therefore, belongs to the space group C_{2h}^2 which requires four asymmetric molecules in the unit cell. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the density of the crystal which was found to be 1.527, is 8 (accurately 8.11). This leads to the conclusion that two molecules of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid associate together to form one asymmetric unit present in the unit cell.

A remarkable feature of the oscillation photographs about a and c axes is that the intensities of spots corresponding to (hkl) planes was very

PLATE I.

Rotation photographs of o-nitrobenzoic acid.

FIG. 1.

a-axis
 $D = 3.50$ cm.

FIG. 2.

b-axis
 $D = 4.00$ cm.

FIG. 3.

c-axis
 $D = 3.60$ cm.

PLATE II.

Rotation photographs of m-nitrobenzoic acid.

FIG. 1.

a-axis
 $D = 5.00$ cm.

FIG. 2.

b-axis
 $D = 4.00$ cm.

FIG. 3.

c-axis
 $D = 4.00$ cm.

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different from that of (hkl) , although the angle β is equal to $91^{\circ}.11\frac{1}{2}'$. This is usually not observed in monoclinic crystals in which the angle differs slightly from 90° .

A note on the results of this crystal (*Current Sci.*, 1938, 6, 44) was published by one of the authors (V. C. T.) in which through mistake the number of molecules in the unit cell has been given incorrectly as 4.

p-Nitrobenzoic Acid.

The crystals of the substance have been found to develop the following faces:

$$c(001), r(101), \rho(10\bar{1}), a(100), q(011) \text{ and } w(11\bar{1}).$$

They belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and the axial ratio found by crystallographic measurements is

$$a : b : c = 2.5615 : 1 : 4.2314 \text{ and } \beta = 96^{\circ}.38 \text{ (cf. Groth, } \textit{ibid.}, \text{ p. 477).}$$

TABLE I.

Axial planes.		P r i s m p l a n e s						hko. (contd.).	
		okl.		hol.		hko.			
001	v. s.	011	v. s.	101	s.	110	v. s.	$\bar{1}\bar{1}0$	s.
002	v. w.	012	m.	102	w.	120	m.	$\bar{1}\bar{2}0$	m. s.
010	w. m.	021	w.	201	m. s.	130	s.	$\bar{1}\bar{3}0$	v. s.
020	s.	031	v. w.	301	m.	140	m. s.	$\bar{1}\bar{4}0$	m. s., m.
030	m. s., s.	$01\bar{1}$	v. s.	$10\bar{1}$	s.	150	w.	$\bar{1}\bar{5}0$	v. w.
040	s.	$01\bar{2}$	w.	$10\bar{2}$	w.	210	m. s.	$\bar{2}\bar{1}0$	m. s.
100	v. s., s.	$02\bar{1}$	m.	$20\bar{1}$	w. m.	220	s.	$\bar{2}\bar{2}0$	m. s.
200	s.	$02\bar{2}$	m.	$20\bar{2}$	m.	230	w. m.	$\bar{2}\bar{3}0$	m. s., m.
300	s.	$03\bar{1}$	m. s.	$30\bar{1}$	w. m.	240	w. m.	$\bar{2}\bar{4}0$	w. m.
		$03\bar{2}$	m. s.			260	w. m.	$\bar{3}\bar{1}0$	m.
		$04\bar{1}$	v. s.			310	m. s., m.	$\bar{3}\bar{2}0$	m.
		$04\bar{2}$	w. m.			320	s.	$\bar{3}\bar{3}0$	w.
		$05\bar{1}$	m.			330	w. m.	$\bar{3}\bar{4}0$	m. s.
		052	w. m.			340	m. s.		
		$06\bar{1}$	w. m.			410	} w.		
		$06\bar{2}$	m.			420			
		$07\bar{1}$	w.						
		$07\bar{2}$	v. w.						

TABLE II.

General planes

111 v. w.	122 m.	211 w.	222 w. m.	311 m.	372 m.
121 m.	131 s.	221 v. w.	231 m. s.	311 m.	311 v. w.
122 m. s.	132 w. m.	231 m.	232 w.	321 w.	321 w.
131 w. m.	141 v. s., s.	211 m. s.	241 w. m.	331 w. m.	331 w.
111 m. s., m.	142 w. m.	221 m.	242 m. s.	341 m. s.	441 m. s.
121 m. s., m.	143 w. m.	222 w. m.	243 w.	351 w.	431 w. m.
122 w.	151 m. s.	231 s.	251 w.	311 w.	441 m. s.
131 m.	152 m. s.	232 w. m.	252 m.	321 m.	442 m. s.
132 m.	161 w.	241 w. m.	261 m.	331 w.	451 m. s.
141 m.	162 w. m.	242 w. m.	272 w. m.	332 w.	
142 w. m.	171 v. w.	251 w. m.	282 m. s.	341 m. s.	
152 m.	172 w. m.	252 w.	211 m.	342 v. w.	
162 m. s.	111 w.	262 w. m.	231 w. m.	351 w. m.	
111 m. s.	112 m.	211 m.		361 w. m.	
112 w. m.	121 w. m.	212 w. m., m.		371 w. m.	
121 s.	131 w. m.	221 m. s.			

TABLE III.

Axial planes.

P r i s m p l a n e s

	okl.	okl. (contd.)	hol.	hko.
001 w. m.	011 w. m.	036 m.	201 m. s.	120 w.
002 w. m.	012 v. w.	041 m.	202 v. w.	130 s.
003 w. m., w.	013 w. m., m.	042 w. m.	203 s.	140 w.
004 w.	014 w. m.	043 w. m., m.	204 m. s., m.	210 m. s.
005 w.	015 w.	044 w.	205 w.	220 v. w.
006 w.	017 w. m.	051 w. m.	206 w. m.	230 m.
007 v. w.	021 w. m.	052 w.	201 v. s.	240 w. m.
020 w. m.	022 m. s.	053 w. m.	202 s.	310 v. w.

TABLE III (contd.).

Axial planes.	P r i s m p l a n e s		
	okl.	ho \bar{l} ₂	hko.
040 m.	023 m., m. s.	20 $\bar{3}$ w. m. ₂	320 w. m.
200 m.	024 w.	20 $\bar{5}$ m. s.	330 w.
400 w. m.	026 v. w.	20 $\bar{6}$ w. m.	340 w.
	027 w.	401 w., w. m. ₂	420 w.
	031 w. m., m.	402 m.	430 w.
	032 w.	403 m. ₂	440 m., w. m.
	033 w.	404 w. ₂ m.	530 w.
	034 w. m., m.	40 $\bar{1}$ m.	
	035 w. m.	40 $\bar{2}$ m. s.	
	054 w.	40 $\bar{3}$ m. s., m.	

TABLE IV.

General planes.

111 v. s.	134 w.	224 m. s.	311 s., m. s.	411 m. s., m.
112 m.	135 m. s., m.	227 w. m.	312 v. s., s.	412 m.
113 s.	13 $\bar{6}$ v. w.	22 $\bar{1}$ v. w.	313 s.	413 m.
114 m.	14 $\bar{1}$ v. w.	22 $\bar{2}$ w. m.	314 m. s., m.	414 m.
116 w. m.	14 $\bar{2}$ w. m.	22 $\bar{3}$ w. m.	315 w.	411 w. m.
11 $\bar{1}$ w.	14 $\bar{3}$ w. m.	22 $\bar{4}$ m.	31 $\bar{1}$ s.	41 $\bar{2}$ w. m.
11 $\bar{2}$ m. s.	151 w.	22 $\bar{5}$ w. m.	31 $\bar{3}$ m.	41 $\bar{3}$ m.
11 $\bar{3}$ w. m., m.	152 v. w.	231 m.	31 $\bar{4}$ w. m.	41 $\bar{5}$ m.
11 $\bar{4}$ w. m.	153 v. w.	233 w. m.	31 $\bar{5}$ w. m.	421 w. m.
11 $\bar{5}$ w.	15 $\bar{1}$ v. w.	234 v. w.	31 $\bar{6}$ w. m.	422 m. s., m.
11 $\bar{6}$ w. m.	15 $\bar{2}$ w. m.	235 w. m.	324 v. w.	423 m.
121 v. s.	15 $\bar{3}$ w. m.	236 v. w.	325 v. w.	424 w.
122 s.		23 $\bar{1}$ m.	32 $\bar{1}$ w. m.	425 w. m.
123 m.		23 $\bar{2}$ v. w.	32 $\bar{2}$ v. w.	426 w.
124 m.		23 $\bar{4}$ w.	32 $\bar{3}$ m.	42 $\bar{1}$ w. m.

TABLE IV (contd.).

General planes.

125 w., v. w	211 m. s., m.	241 v. w.	324 w. m.	422 w.
127 w.	212 v. s.	243 v. w.	333 w.	425 m.
121 w. m.	213 v. s., s.	245 v. w.	334 m.	431 w. m.
122 w.	214 w. m.	241 v. w.	335 v. w.	432 m., w. m.
124 m.	215 w. m., m.	242 m.	331 v. w.	433 w. m.
127 w.	211 m. s., m.	243 w. m.	332 w. m.	434 w. m.
132 m.	212 w. m.	243 w. m.	341 w. m.	435 m.
133 m.	213 w. m.	251 v. w.	342 v. w.	431 w. m.
134 w. m., m.	214 m.	252 v. w.	343 w.	432 w. m.
135 v. m.	215 m., m. s.	253 w. m.	344 w. m.	433 w.
136 w.	216 w. m.		345 w. m.	442 w. m., w.
131 m.	217 w.		341 m. s.	443 m.
132 w.	221 m.		342 v. w.	511 w.
	222 s.		343 v. w.	513 v. w.
	223 m. s.		351 v. w.	511 w.
				513 w., v. w.
				521 w.
				522 v. w.
				531 w.

TABLE V.

Axial planes.

P r i s m p l a n e s

	okl.	hol.	hol.	hko _z
1	2	3	4	5
002 m. s., m.	011 w. m.	202 v. s.		120 s.
008 w. m.	012 w. m.	20(10) m. s.	404 s.	210 w. m.
020 m	013 w. m., m.	202 m., w. m.	406 w.	220 w. m.
200 v. s.	015 v. s., s.	204 w. m.	408 w. m., m.	320 w., w. m.
600 w. m.	017 w.	206 w. m., m.	604 w. m.	420 w.
	019 v. w.	2010 m.	600 } w., m.	510 m.
			602 }	

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TABLE V (contd.).

Axial planes.	okl.	hol	Prism planes.	
	022 w.	402 m.		520 w. m.
	024 m., w. m.	404 m. s.	604 m.	
	025 w. m.	408 w.	606 m.	
	026 w. m.	402 w. m.	804 w. m.	
02(10)	w. m.			

TABLE VI.

General planes.

113 w.m., m.	121 s.	211 m.	223 m.	311 w. m., m.	411 w. m., m.
{	114 w. m.	120 s.	212 w.	224 w. m.	315 m.
	115 m. s., s.	122 m. s.	213 m.	225 w.m.	317 w. m.
116 w. m.	124 m.s.	215 w. m.	226 w.m.	318 w. m.	415 v. w.
117 m.	125 w.	217 m. s.	227 w.m., m.	319 w.	416 v. w.
118 m.	126 w.m.	219 v. w.	228 m.s., m.	313 m. s.	417 m.
11(10) v. w.	129 w.	211 m. s.	229 m.s.	314 v. s.	412 w.
113 m.		212 w.		315 m.	413 w.
114 w. m.		213 v. s.		316 m. s.	416 w.
115 v. s.		215 w.		317 m. s., s.	417 w. m., m.
117 v. s.		216 m. s.		319 w.	421 m.
118 w. m.		217 w. m., m.		322 w. m.	424 w. m.
119 m. s., s.		218 w. m.		324 m.	421 v. w.
121 w.		219 m s., m.		326 w.	
122 w. m., m.		221 w. m.		328 w.	
123 w.		222 w.		322 w. m.	
124 w.		226 w.m.		323 w.	
126 w.		227 w.		324 w. m.	
		221 w. m.		326 w. m., m.	
		222 m., m. s.		327 m.	

TABLE VI (contd.).

General planes.

511 w. m.	611 w.
512 m.	613 w.
513 w.	61 $\bar{1}$ w m.
517 w.	61 $\bar{3}$ w.
511 w. m., m.	615 v. w.
51 $\bar{2}$ m. s.	61 $\bar{7}$ w.
51 $\bar{3}$ w.	
51 $\bar{5}$ w.	
519 m, s.	
521 w.	
522 v. w.	
524 w. m.	

The lengths of the axes determined from the rotation photographs (Plate III, FIG. 1--3) about a , b and c axes are $a=12.95 \text{ \AA}$, $b=5.04 \text{ \AA}$, $c=21.31 \text{ \AA}$.

These give the axial ratio $a : b : c = 2.569 : 1 : 4.229$ which is in good agreement with that mentioned above.

The list of reflecting planes observed in the crystal with their approximate relative intensities is given in Tables V and VI.

It will be seen from these that planes (hol) are halved when either h or l or $(h+1)$ is odd and (oro) is also halved. This shows that the crystal belongs to the space group C_{2h}^2 which requires four asymmetric molecules in the unit cell. The number of molecules in the unit cell calculated from its dimensions and the density of the crystals which was found to be 1.61, is 8 (accurately 8.03). This again leads to the conclusions that two molecules of *p*-nitrobenzoic acid associate together to form one asymmetric unit present in the unit cell.

The association of molecules in the unit cell observed in the case of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids is not an improbability and has been observed in several cases by previous workers (*cf.* Caspari, *Phil. Mag.*, 1927, **4**, 1276; Prasad, D'Souza and Shanker, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1936; Banerjee, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1937).

PLATE III.

Rotation photographs of p-nitrobenzoic acid.

FIG. 1.

a-axis,
 $D = 4.00$ cm.

FIG. 2.

b-axis
 $D = 4.00$ cm.

FIG. 3.

c-axis
 $D = 4.00$ cm.

